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Research Article

PREPARATION AND EVALUATION OF OCULAR INSERTS FOR CONTROLLED DELIVERY OF GATIFLOXACIN SESQUEHYDRATE

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ABSTRACT

Gatifloxacin sesquehydrate is a fluoroquinolone anti-infective agent useful in the treatment of eye infection such as conjunctivitis, keratitis and keratoconjunctivitis. An attempt has been made in the present research to formulate ocular inserts of gatifloxacin sesquehydrate to increase residence time and prolong drug release. Drug reservoir was prepared using hydrophilic polymers like hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), methylcellulose (MC), while rate-controlling membrane was prepared using hydrophobic ethyl cellulose (EC). Ocular inserts were evaluated for their physicochemical parameters like uniformity of thickness, weight, drug content, % moisture absorption, % moisture loss and surface pH. The *in vitro* drug release studies were carried out using bi-chambered donor receiver compartment model. Since targeted prolong release was observed in formulation GFEC6 and GFEC11, these formulations were further subjected to *in vivo* drug release study using rabbits as an animal model. *In vitro* drug release data was treated according to zero order, first order, Higuchi and Kresmer equations to access the mechanism of drug release. Correlation between *in vitro* and *in vivo* drug release was found to be strong revealing the efficacy of the formulation. The drug was found to be active against selected microorganisms as was proved by microbial efficacy studies. Shelf life of the product was found to be more than 2 years. Formulation GFEC6 has achieved target of present study such as increase residence time, prolong drug release, reduction in frequency of administration, and, thus may improve the patient compliance.

Introduction

The physiological constraints imposed by the protective mechanisms of the eye lead to low absorption of drugs and a short duration of the therapeutic effect on ocular drug delivery. Upon instillation of the eye drops only 1–10% of the drug is bioavailable while the rest is drained out of the eye through lacrimal secretions^[1]. To overcome this problem various approaches have been reported, such as ointments, inserts and aqueous gels, to increase the ocular residence time of topically applied medication.

Controlled drug delivery to the eye offer several advantages over conventional therapies like drug solutions or suspensions as eye drops^[2,3]. Ophthalmic inserts offer many advantages over conventional dosage forms, like increased ocular residence, possibility of releasing drugs at a slow and constant rate, accurate dosing, and exclusion of preservatives, increased shelf life and reduced systemic absorption^[4,5]. Several reports revealed improved ocular therapy by ophthalmic inserts. Frequency of instillation of gentamycin sulfate was reduced by a long-acting ophthalmic insert^[6]. O-butyl ester prodrug of tilisolol and the O-palmitoyl ester prodrug of tilisolol were incorporated into an ophthalmic

insert to control drug release^[7]. Di Colo G. and co-researcher^[8] observed respective contributions of diffusion and erosion to the release mechanism of drugs, namely prednisolone, oxytetracycline hydrochloride and gentamycin sulphate through erodible ophthalmic inserts based on poly (ethylene oxide).

Gatifloxacin (1-cyclopropyl-6-fluoro-1, 4-dihydro-8-methoxy-7-[3-methyl-1-piperazinyl]-4-oxo-3-quinolinecarboxylic acid sesquehydrate), a synthetic broad-spectrum antimicrobial fluoroquinolone, that is active against both gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria, is used in the treatment of a wide range of infections such as conjunctivitis, keratitis and keratoconjunctivitis^[9]. The anti-bacterial activity of gatifloxacin sesquehydrate result from inhibition of DNA gyrase (topoisomerase II) and topoisomerase IV, the enzyme that plays a key role in partitioning of the chromosomal DNA during bacterial cell division^[10]. It is presently available as eye drops 0.3%. It is administered at dosing interval of 1 drop every two hours in the affected eye^[11]. The eye drops types dosage form is convenient to use but most of the drug is diluted by tear and rapidly washed out of the sac by constant tear flow

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which can be avoided by using insert by which the therapeutic efficacy of ophthalmic drug can greatly improved^[12].

In the present study, an attempt has been made to formulate ocular insert of gatifloxacin sesquihydrate using hydrophilic polymers like hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), methylcellulose (MC) and PEG 400 as plasticizer, while rate-controlling membrane was prepared using hydrophobic ethyl cellulose (EC) and dibutyl phthalate as plasticizer by solvent casting method with aim of increasing the residence time, achieving controlled release, reduction in frequency of administration and greater therapeutic efficacy.

Materials and methods

Materials

Gatifloxacin sesquihydrate was obtained as gift sample from Medley pharmaceutical Pvt. Ltd., Daman, India. Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC 15 cps), methyl cellulose (MC 400 cps), Ethyl cellulose (EC 15 cps) were obtained from SD Fine chemicals, Mumbai, India. Polyethylene glycol 400 (PEG 400) and Dibutyl phthalate were purchased from Nice chemicals, Cochin. All other reagents and solvent used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of Drug Reservoir

The inserts were prepared by solvent casting method^[13]. The twelve batches (GFEC1 to GFEC12) of gatifloxacin sesquihydrate ocular inserts were prepared using different proportion of drug and polymers such as 1:0.5, 1:1, 1:1.5, 1:0.2, 1:0.4 and 1:0.6 (Table 1). The polymer was dissolved in distilled water (10 ml) and PEG 400 (30% w/w of dry polymer) was added as plasticizer to this solution under stirring condition. The weighed amount of Gatifloxacin sesquihydrate (0.570 g, passed through sieve # 400) was added to above solution and stirred for 12 h to get uniform dispersion. After proper mixing the casting solution (5 ml) was poured in clean glass petridish (Anumbra area 63.59 cm²) and covered with an inverted funnel to allow slow and uniform evaporation at room temperature for 48 h. The dried films thus obtained were cut by cork borer into circular pieces of definite size (8 mm diameter) containing of 2.25 mg of drug^[13,14]. The ocular inserts were then stored in an airtight container (desiccator) under ambient condition.

Preparation of rate controlling membrane

Rate controlling membrane was prepared using two different concentration of ethyl cellulose (4% and 6%) and employing dibutyl phthalate as a plasticizer (Table 1). Dibutyl phthalate was used in the concentration of 30% w/w based on the weight of dry polymer. Films were prepared by solvent casting method using acetone as a casting solvent. After drying at room temperature circular rings of 10 mm diameter were cut using cork borer and used to seal both the sides of the drug reservoir to control release from the periphery^[15].

Characterization of prepared ocular inserts

Uniformity of thickness

The thickness of the insert was determined using a Vernier caliper (Mitotoyo, Japan) at five separate points of each insert. For each formulation, five randomly selected inserts were tested for their thickness^[15].

Uniformity of weight

From each batch, five inserts were taken out and weighed individually using digital balance (Asco, India). The mean weight of the insert was noted^[15].

Drug content

Five ocular inserts were taken from each batch and dissolved or crushed in 10 ml of isotonic phosphate buffer pH 7.4 in a beaker and were filtered into 25 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark with buffer. One ml of the above solution was withdrawn and the absorbance was measured by UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Systronics -2202, India) at 285.6 nm after suitable dilutions^[16].

% Moisture absorption

The percentage moisture absorption test was carried out to check physical stability or integrity of the film at humid condition. The films were weighed and placed in desiccator containing saturated solution of aluminium chloride and 84% humidity was maintained^[17]. After three days, the films were taken out and reweighed^[18]. The % moisture absorption was calculated using the formulae

$$\left[\% \text{Moisture absorption} = \frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100 \right]$$

% Moisture loss

The percentage moisture loss was carried out to check the integrity of the film at dry condition. The films were weighted and kept in dessicator containing anhydrous calcium chloride. After three days, the films were taken out and reweighed^[19]. The percentage moisture loss was calculated using the formulae

$$\% \text{Moisture loss} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

Surface pH

The inserts were allowed to swell in closed petridish at room temperature for 30 minutes in 0.1 ml of bidistilled water. The swollen device was removed and placed under digital pH meter (Elico, India) to determine the surface pH^[20].

Drug - excipients compatibility study

Fourier transport infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR absorption spectra of the pure drug, placebo formulations (without drug) and drug loaded selected formulation (GFEC6 and GFEC11) were recorded in the range of 400 - 4000 cm⁻¹ by KBr disc method (2 mg sample in 200 mg KBr) using FTIR spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer, Spectrum GX, Chicago IL, USA).

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Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) scans of pure drug, placebo formulations and drug loaded selected ocular inserts (GFEC6 and GFEC11) were performed using DSC-PYRIS-1 (Perkin-Elmer, USA). The analysis was performed with a heating range of 50-480°C and a rate of 10° C min⁻¹.

In vitro diffusion study

The *in vitro* diffusion of drug from the different ocular insert was studied using the classical standard cylindrical tube fabricated in the laboratory (bi-chambered donor receptor compartment model). A simple modification of glass tube of 15 mm internal diameter and 100 mm height^[21] The diffusion cell membrane (prehydrated cellophane)^[22] was tied to one end of open cylinder, which acted as a donor compartment. An ocular insert was placed inside this compartment. The diffusion cell membrane acted as corneal epithelium. The entire surface of the membrane was in contact with the receptor compartment comprising of 25 ml of isotonic phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) in a 100 ml beaker^[23,24]. The content of receptor compartment was stirred continuously using a magnetic stirrer and temperature was maintained at 37° ± 0.5°C. At specific intervals of time, 1 ml aliquot of solution was withdrawn from the receptor compartment and replaced with fresh buffer solution. The aliquot was analyzed for the drug content using UV-VIS spectrophotometer at 285.6 nm after appropriate dilutions against reference using isotonic phosphate buffer pH 7.4 as blank.

Release kinetics

In order to understand the mechanism and kinetics of drug release, the results of the *in vitro* drug release study were fitted with various kinetic equations such as zero order (% release vs t), first order (log% unrelease vs t), Higuchi matrix (% release vs square root of time). In order to define a model which will represent a better fit for the formulation, drug release data further analysed by Peppas equation, $Mt/M\infty = kt^n$, where Mt is the amount of drug released at time t and $M\infty$ is the amount released at time ∞ , the $Mt/M\infty$ is the fraction of drug released at time t , k is the kinetic constant and n is the diffusional exponent, a measure of the primary mechanism of drug release. r^2 values were calculated for the linear curves obtained by regression analysis of the above plots^[25].

Sterilization and interaction study

The selected ocular inserts (GFEC6 and GFEC11) were serialized by gamma radiation (Gamma I-radiation chamber 5000, Brit, India) before eye irritancy and *in vivo* study. Ocular inserts were packaged in aluminum foil. The package was exposed to a total dose of 2.5 mega rads^[26]. After sterilization, the ocular inserts were also evaluated for sterility test according Indian Pharmacopocia. Interaction studies were carried out to investigate any interaction between drug and polymers, as well as to study the effect of gamma radiation on drug after

sterilization. Interaction studies were carried by UV scanning, infrared studies and assay of ocular inserts^[27].

Eye irritancy test

The selected ocular inserts (GFEC6 and GFEC11) were sterilized using γ -radiation before eye irritancy test^[28] (OECD guideline, test guideline 405, 2002) and *in vivo* drug release studies. The OECD guideline for eye irritancy test is currently the most valuable and reliable method for evaluating hazard or safety of a substance introduced into or around the eye. Eye irritancy potential of a substance was determined on the basis of its ability to cause injury to the cornea, iris, and conjunctiva when a substance is applied to the eye^[29]. Testing was carried out on adult albino rabbits weighing about 2.5 to 3.5 kg of either sex. All rabbits were maintained under 12 h light and dark cycles and were fed with green vegetables throughout the course of study. Food and water was allowed ad libitum. A twelve rabbits were used for testing the eye irritation potential of the ocular inserts. Ocular inserts were placed into the cul-de-sac of the rabbit while other eye served as a control^[19,24].

In vivo drug release study

Selected ocular inserts (GFEC6 and GFEC11) sterilized using γ -radiations were used for *in vivo* drug release studies. Two groups containing six healthy rabbits^[30] were used to study the drug release *in vivo* from formulations which showed the desired *in vitro* drug release. Each rabbit was kept in good hygienic condition in order to avoid vulnerability to any disease including ophthalmic type. Selected ocular inserts were placed in the cul-de-sac of each rabbit while the other eye served as a control. At periodic intervals (2, 4, 6, 8, 12 and 24 hrs) the inserts were taken out carefully from the cul-de-sac of each rabbit and analyzed for the remaining drug content. The drug remaining was subtracted from the initial drug content of the insert, which gave the amount of drug released in the rabbit eye.^[19,24]

Microbiological studies

The selected ocular insert were evaluated for microbiological study. The microbiological studies were carried out to ascertain the biological activity of the selected formulation against test microorganism. A Layer of nutrient agar seeded with the test organism (E. coli and S.aureus) was allowed to solidify in the Petri dish. An ocular inserts were removed from the pack and carefully placed over the agar layer at a suitable distance^[26]. The plates were then incubated at 37± 0.5°C for 24 h. After incubation the zone of inhibition was measured around the ocular insert.

Stability study

Stability studies were carried out on ocular inserts GFEC6 and GFEC11, according to ICH guidelines^[31]. A sufficient number of ocular inserts (packed in aluminum foil) were stored in humidity chamber, with relative humidity of 75 % and at temperature of 40 ± 0.5°C. The samples were tested for drug content after 0, 30, 60, 90 and 180 days respectively^[27]. The degradation rate

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constant was determined from the plot of the percentage drug remained vs. time in days^[26].

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{-K}{2.303}$$

Where, K is the degradation rate constant.

Results and Discussion

Uniformity of thickness

The thickness of the ocular inserts varied between 0.263 ± 0.0054 mm to 0.352 ± 0.0036 mm (Table 2). The formulations did not produce any irritation when placed in the cul de sac since they were not thick enough to produce irritation.

Uniformity of weight

The weight of the ocular inserts were found to be in the range of 21.94 ± 0.6333 to 26.51 ± 0.4475 mg (Table 2). The uniformity of the weights of the films indicates good distribution of the drug, polymer and plasticizer.

Drug content

For the various formulations, drug content was found to vary between 2.158 ± 0.0081 to 2.245 ± 0.0054 mg (Table 2). The drug content was found to be almost same with their low standard deviation values.

% Moisture absorption

The results of % moisture absorption are shown in the Table 2. The % moisture absorption was more in GFEC5 (9.26 ± 0.2014) due to HPMC (which is hydrophilic in nature) and 4% EC as rate controlling membrane which was very thin when compared to 6 % EC. This is assumed that less concentration of ethyl cellulose offered minimum hindrance to the transfer of moisture. In contrast, while formulation GFEC8 (4.67 ± 0.1919) had shown low moisture absorption which may be due to the high concentration of ethyl cellulose as a rate controlling membrane.

% Moisture loss

The % moisture loss study revealed that formulation GFEC11 (12.97 ± 0.2931) showed high moisture loss may be due to less hindrance offered by ethyl cellulose (4%). Formulation GFEC2 (7.12 ± 0.2488) showed less moisture loss might due to presence of more hydrophilic polymer (HPMC) and high concentration of ethyl cellulose (EC 6%). The formulations with low concentration of ethyl cellulose (EC 4%) had more tendencies to lose moisture as compared to those containing high concentration of ethyl cellulose (EC 6%). The results are shown in the Table 2.

Surface pH

The surface pH of prepared inserts was found to be in range of 6.25 ± 0.0358 to 7.25 ± 0.0268 (Table 2). This indicates that the prepared inserts would not alter the pH of the tear fluid in the eye.

Drug – Excipients compatibility study

Fourier transport infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR spectra of pure drug, placebo formulations (without drug) and drug loaded ocular inserts were recorded. The results are shown in the Figure 1 and 2. The two peaks at 1281.59 nm and 1447.89 nm for the –C=O stretching of –COOH and CH bending of CH₃ group respectively. The peaks at 1663.19 nm, 2843.01 nm, 2975.69 and 821.53 nm show as major peaks for drug. All the above peaks are also present in drug loaded ocular inserts that confirms the presence of drug in the polymer without any interaction.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

The results of DSC study are given in Figure 3 and 4. DSC thermograms showed endothermic peak of Gatifloxacin sesquihydrate at 190°C, which corresponded to its melting point. Thermograms of drug loaded ocular inserts showed peak at 189.209°C and 189.564°C, Placebo formulations (without drug) showed at 366.955°C and 365.304°C. There was a slight decrease in the melting point of drug when prepared in the form of ocular inserts. The evaluation of the thermograms obtained from DSC revealed no interaction between the polymer and the drug in the ocular inserts.

In vitro diffusion study

In the present study, *in vitro* drug release was carried out in triplicate. At different time intervals, the sample was withdrawn and cumulative percentage drug release was calculated on the basis of mean amount of drug present in the respective films. *In vitro* drug release study for formulations GFEC1 to GFEC12 revealed that these formulations were capable of extending the drug release up to 24 hr. The percentage drug release of all the formulations is presented in Figure 5. The formulations which showed better physicochemical parameters with desired drug release were selected. The release of drug from the selected formulations GFEC6 and GFEC11 were found to be 77.08% and 83.43% at the end of 24 hours. The selected formulations were then evaluated for further studies such as release kinetic, eye irritation test, *in vivo* study, microbiological study and stability study.

Release kinetics

The *in vitro* release profile was analyzed by various kinetic models. The kinetic models used were zero order, first order, Higuchi and Krosmeier Peppas equations. The release constants were calculated from the slope of the respective plots (Table 3). Higher correlation was observed with zero order plots ($r^2 > 0.99$) than first order and Higuchi equation. It was observed from zero order plots that the drug diffused slowly from ocular inserts. For planer geometry, the value of $n=0.5$ indicates a Fickian diffusion mechanism, for $0.5 < n < 1.0$, indicates anomalous (non-fickian) transport, and $n=1$ implies case II (relaxation controlled) transport¹⁹. In the present systems, the value for n was found to be in the range of 0.708 to 1.059 indicating that the release mechanisms followed anomalous (non-fickian) transport and zero order release (case II transport). The selected

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formulations GFEC6 and GFEC11 were having 'n' value 0.882 and 1.059 respectively, indicating that the release mechanism followed anomalous (non-fickian) transport and zero order release (case II transport).

Sterilization and interaction study

The selected inserts ((GFEC6 and GFEC11) were sterilized using γ -radiation before carrying out the eye irritancy and *in vivo* drug release study. Sterilized inserts were tested for sterility as per Indian Pharmacopocia. No microbial or fungal growth was seen in any of the formulations, which indicated that the films were sterilized completely. All γ -irradiated inserts complied sterility test IP. No interaction between drug and polymer due to sterilization by gamma radiation was found when tested by UV absorption studies and FTIR study. The UV absorption spectra for pure drug before and after sterilization showed similar pattern. The same peaks were observed in the FTIR spectra of sterile drug as that of parent Gatifloxacin sesquehydrate. This shows that the drug was not changed chemically, revealing the suitability of γ -radiation for the sterilization of ocular inserts.

Eye irritancy test

Eye irritancy test was carried out with selected ocular inserts (GFEC6 and GFEC11) before undertaking the *in vivo* release study. Results of the eye irritancy test revealed that all inserts prepared using drug reservoir (HPMC and MC) and ethyl cellulose as rate controlling membrane were nontoxic and non-irritating to the eye, as total score was zero. As inserts were not expelled out of the cul-de-sac of the rabbits, it suggests that the insert's dimensions were appropriate for use.

In vivo drug release study

Formulations GFEC6 and GFEC11 were chosen for *in vivo* drug release study. *In vivo* release studies were performed using rabbits. Ocular inserts were removed carefully at periodic intervals (2, 4, 6, 8, 12 and 24 hrs) and analyzed for residual drug content. The drug remaining was subtracted from the initial drug content of the insert, which gave the amount of drug released in the rabbit eye. The results are presented in Figure 6. The *in vivo* drug release study from formulations GFEC6 and GFEC11 were found to be in accordance with that of the *in vitro* drug release study. Hence, we tried to correlate *in vivo* results with the *in vitro* percentage drug release. The

correlation values were found to be 0.9975 and 0.9962 for formulations GFEC6 and GFEC11 respectively. The linearity was found in both formulations but formulation GFEC6 exhibited a good correlation and better linearity (Figure 7). The strong *in vitro* and *in vivo* correlation revealed the efficacy of the formulation. There was no drag out of circular inserts at the time of experiment which suggest that the particular dimension (10 mm) was suitable as ocular inserts.

Microbiological studies

The selected ocular inserts (GFEC6 and GFEC11) showed antimicrobial activity when tested microbiologically on solidified agar. Clear zone of inhibition were obtained in said formulations against both test organisms (Table 4).

Stability study

Accelerated stability studies at elevated temperature and humidity revealed no significant change in drug content after 180 days. Ocular inserts could be stored safely at study temperature. However, storage temperature not in excess of 40°C. The degradation rate constant for formulations GFEC6 and GFEC11 were found to be 1.3691×10^{-4} and $1.4187 \times 10^{-4} \text{ day}^{-1}$, respectively as shown in Figure 8. The overall degradation is less than 5%, a tentative shelf-life of 2 years may be assigned to formulation as per ICH guidelines.

Conclusion

Various batches of gatifloxacin sesquehydrate ocular inserts were prepared using solvent casting method and evaluated. Reservoir type ocular inserts (formulation GFEC6) consisting of a hydroxylpropyl methylcellulose reservoir with gatifloxacin sesquehydrate (1:1.5) and rate controlling membranes of ethyl cellulose (6%) satisfied all the pharmaceutical parameters of ocular inserts and demonstrated sustained release of the drug in the eye over the period of 24 hrs. The said promising formulation would be able to offer benefits such as increase residence time, prolonged drug release, reduction in frequency of administration and there by may help to improve the patient compliance with the limitation that formulation is non-erodible. Further work may be carried out to establish the therapeutic utility of this system by pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic studies in human beings.

Table 1: Composition of gatifloxacin sesquehydrate ocular inserts

Formulation code	Drug reservoir				Rate controlling membrane EC (%)
	Drug (g)	HPMC(g)	MC(g)	Drug: Polymer ratio	
GFEC1	0.570	0.285	-	1:05	4%
GFEC2	0.570	0.285	-	1:05	6%
GFEC3	0.570	0.570	-	1:1	4%
GFEC4	0.570	0.570	-	1:1	6%
GFEC5	0.570	0.855	-	1:1.5	4%
GFEC6	0.570	0.855	-	1:1.5	6%
GFEC7	0.570	-	0.114	1:0.2	4%
GFEC8	0.570	-	0.114	1:0.2	6%

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GFEC9	0.570	-	0.228	1:0.4	4%
GFEC10	0.570	-	0.228	1:0.4	6%
GFEC11	0.570	-	0.342	1:0.6	4%
GFEC12	0.570	-	0.342	1:0.6	6%
Casting solvent	Water (10ml)				Acetone (10ml)
Plasticizer	PEG 400 (30%w/w of dry polymer)				Dibutyl phthalate (30%w/w of dry polymer)

Table 2: Physicochemical evaluation of ocular inserts

Formulation code	Weight (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (mg)	Surface pH	% Moisture Absorption	% Moisture Loss
GFEC1	23.22 ± 0.3690	0.296 ± 0.0044	2.223±0.0084	6.83 ± 0.0465	6.34 ± 0.2319	8.43 ± 0.2775
GFEC2	25.28 ± 0.4421	0.338 ± 0.0046	2.223±0.0084	6.75 ± 0.0587	5.46 ± 0.1904	7.12 ± 0.2488
GFEC3	24.12 ± 0.4178	0.306 ± 0.0055	2.158 ± 0.0081	6.56 ± 0.0179	6.94 ± 0.1409	9.32 ± 0.3038
GFEC4	25.84 ± 0.6343	0.348 ± 0.0063	2.158 ± 0.0081	6.75 ± 0.0268	5.84 ± 0.1779	7.96 ± 0.2322
GFEC5	24.64 ± 0.5975	0.314 ± 0.0041	2.245 ± 0.0054	6.77 ± 0.0179	9.26 ± 0.2014	10.56 ± 0.3903
GFEC6	26.51 ± 0.4475	0.352 ± 0.0036	2.245 ± 0.0054	7.13 ± 0.0268	7.44 ± 0.2862	8.25 ± 0.2063
GFEC7	21.94 ± 0.6333	0.259 ± 0.0030	2.199 ± 0.0076	6.50 ± 0.0820	5.35 ± 0.1215	10.12 ± 0.3362
GFEC8	23.90 ± 0.6460	0.297 ± 0.0053	2.199 ± 0.0076	6.67 ± 0.0447	4.67 ± 0.1919	8.24 ± 0.3340
GFEC9	22.39 ± 0.5833	0.263 ± 0.0054	2.162 ± 0.0065	6.25 ± 0.0358	5.89 ± 0.2261	10.46 ± 0.3856
GFEC10	24.43 ± 0.7373	0.301 ± 0.0067	2.162 ± 0.0065	6.50 ± 0.0179	4.74 ± 0.1376	9.88 ± 0.2677
GFEC11	23.05 ± 0.5732	0.278 ± 0.0027	2.223 ± 0.0105	7.25 ± 0.0268	7.86 ± 0.1661	12.97 ± 0.2931
GFEC12	24.89 ± 0.7018	0.312 ± 0.0044	2.223 ± 0.0105	7.03 ± 0.0931	6.10 ± 0.2318	10.14 ± 0.2073

*Values as Mean ± SD (n = 5)

Table 3: Kinetic data of drug release from GFEC1 to GFEC12

Formulation Codes	Zero Order Kinetic		First Order Kinetic			Higuchi's Model		Krosemeyer Peppas model		
	K ₀	r ²	Slope	K ₁	r ²	K _h	r ²	K _p	n	r ²
GFEC1	3.797	0.9907	-0.048	-0.111	0.9218	23.27	0.9723	7.530	0.778	0.9944
GFEC2	3.730	0.9923	-0.043	-0.100	0.9304	23.02	0.9663	6.692	0.805	0.9892
GFEC3	3.543	0.9968	-0.035	-0.081	0.9422	22.07	0.9636	5.341	0.858	0.9929
GFEC4	3.454	0.9976	-0.032	-0.074	0.9467	21.72	0.9605	4.409	0.910	0.9930
GFEC5	3.292	0.9999	-0.028	-0.064	0.9504	20.85	0.9638	3.419	0.986	0.9997

K: release rate constant; r²: Coefficient of determination; n: release exponent

Table 4: In vitro inhibition of the growth of microorganisms by selected ocular insert

Formulation code	Zone of inhibition (mm)	
	S. Aureus	E. Coli
GFEC6	41.8 ± 3.084	36.0 ± 2.582
GFEC11	46.6 ± 3.169	42.6 ± 3.098

*Values as Mean ± SD (n = 3)

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Figure 1: FTIR spectra of pure Gatifloxacin (A), Placebo film of HPMC (without drug) (B), Placebo film of EC (without drug) (C), Drug loaded formulation GFEC6 (D)

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Figure 2: FTIR spectra of pure Gatifloxacin (A), Placebo film of MC (without drug) (B), Placebo film of EC (without drug) (C), Drug loaded Formulation GFEC11 (D)

Figure 3: DSC thermograms of pure Gatifloxacin (S1), Placebo film of HPMC (without drug) (S2), Placebo film of EC (without drug) (S3), Drug loaded formulation GEEC6 (S4)

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Figure 4: DSC thermograms of pure Gatifloxacin (S1), Placebo film of MC (without drug) (S2), Placebo film of EC (without drug) (S3), Drug loaded formulation GFEC11 (S4)

Figure 5: In vitro diffusion of Gatifloxacin sesquihydrate from GFEC1 to GFEC12 formulations

Figure 6: In vivo diffusion of Gatifloxacin sesquihydrate from GFEC6 and GFEC11 formulations

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Figure 7: In vitro and In vivo correlation study of GFEC6 formulation

Figure 8: Plot of log% of drug remained vs. time for ocular inserts GFEC6 and GFEC11

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